

Random Ray Adjoint Driven Variance Reduction for Fast Reactors with OpenMC

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ABSTRACT

A random ray transport solver has recently been added to OpenMC to facilitate the generation of adjoint-based weight windows for reducing the variance of high-fidelity continuous energy Monte Carlo simulations. In the present work, we test the efficiency of the new random ray-based FW-CADIS variance reduction workflow in OpenMC on a lead-cooled fast reactor simulation, which features tallies in heavily shielded locations outside of the core. A comparison is made against OpenMC's MAGIC-generated weight windows. Random ray FW-CADIS weight windows are found to be 12.5× faster to generate as compared to MAGIC and are up to 93× more efficient for local variance reduction.

Keywords: OpenMC, Monte Carlo, Random Ray, Variance Reduction, LFR

1. INTRODUCTION

Continuous energy Monte Carlo (MC) is a high-fidelity method for neutral particle transport. It is commonly used as the “gold-standard” for simulations in the fields of both fission reactor and fusion device modeling, owing to the minimal number of physical approximations made by the method. The MC method functions by tracking the histories of individual particles from their birth (e.g., from a fission event or from a fixed external source term) to their death (e.g., being absorbed, causing a fission, or escaping the geometry). A critical aspect of this method is that, for analog MC simulations, the integration particle density (i.e., where the simulated particles travel and generate tallies for) is correlated exactly with the actual physical particle distribution of the problem being simulated. A major downside to this characteristic is that the MC method struggles to produce useful information for regions of the problem with very low particle flux. For instance, if a thick shield wall is placed between a source and a detector such that the expected flux at the detector is 10^{12} times lower than at the source, then it may require simulating about 10^{12} particles to generate a single tally/score to the detector. In practice, this often makes problems featuring significant shielding impossible to simulate with analog Monte Carlo.

1.1. Monte Carlo Variance Reduction

To remedy this fundamental problem with MC particle transport, a wide variety of variance reduction techniques have been developed. One common technique is to define a set of “Weight Windows” (WW) on some mesh overlaying the geometry. If a particle travels into a weight window where the particle's weight w (which by default starts life with weight 1.0) is above the bounds of the weight window, it can “split” into several copies of itself (while conserving total aggregate weight) such that the weight distributed to each of the particles now fits into the weight window's accepted range. Conversely, if a particle travels into a weight window where the particle's weight is below the bounds of the weight

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window, it can “roulette”, where a random sample is taken, which decides if particles are either terminated or survive and have their weight increased to fit within the weight window (again, conserving total aggregate weight on average). If an optimal choice for weight window values is made, particles can be encouraged to explore (in a controlled and unbiased manner) areas of low physical flux, and discouraged from over-exploring areas of high particle flux. In this manner, variance can be reduced either globally (such that all regions of phase space have approximately equal variance), or in a targeted manner (such that particles are funneled towards a particular area of interest, such as a detector).

While weight windows are relatively unobtrusive and straightforward to *use* in a Monte Carlo code, the problem arises with how to generate high efficiency weight window parameters. A poor set of weight windows can have no effect on the simulation, or can cause overly aggressive particle splitting (making the simulation of even a single starting particle take an impractically long time). The mathematically ideal choice of weight windows can be computed if the adjoint flux distribution is known, via the Consistent Adjoint Driven Importance Sampling (CADIS) [1] or Forward-Weighted CADIS (FW-CADIS) [2] methods. However, we typically do not know the exact flux or adjoint flux distributions before we begin a MC simulation — if we did, we would have no reason to perform the simulation. However, an *approximate* adjoint flux distribution often suffices when used for weight window generation, allowing for the usage of faster (but reduced-fidelity) transport methods for determining the approximate adjoint flux distribution.

1.2. Weight Window Generation

There are a variety of existing workflows for producing estimates of the global adjoint flux distribution for weight window generation. Several popular options today are:

- ADVANTG [3] + Denovo [4] for MCNP [5] — This workflow homogenizes the MCNP geometry onto a regular Cartesian mesh, then computes the adjoint for the simplified grid model with the Denovo discrete ordinates (S_N) transport code.
- ATTILA [6] and ATTILA4MC [7] for MCNP — This workflow “remeshes” the input geometry onto an unstructured mesh, then computes the adjoint on the unstructured mesh using a discrete ordinates solver.
- OpenMC — This workflow uses an internal random ray solver that operates natively on the same geometry that the Monte Carlo solvers uses (either constructive solid geometry, CAD, or unstructured mesh).
- SCONE [8] — This workflow is similar to OpenMC in that it uses an internal random ray solver, though does not support as many geometry types (e.g., CAD) as OpenMC.

Comparing these workflows, the OpenMC workflow is notable as it requires no coupling between multiple external applications and no spatial homogenization or remeshing is performed (both of which can be troublesome from a practical standpoint). We also note that OpenMC also has a forward flux-based method for computing weight windows (using the MAGIC method [9]), though weight windows generated via MAGIC may have limited efficiency as they are not based on adjoint fluxes.

2. OPENMC

OpenMC is a Monte Carlo neutral particle transport application, which contains several methods for reducing the variance of the Monte Carlo solver. Adjoint driven weight window generation in OpenMC is accomplished via an internal random ray adjoint solver. This recently added workflow is highly automated, with the user performing the following steps:

1. The user starts with a working continuous energy (CE) Monte Carlo OpenMC input deck (typically in the form of a fully composed Python Model instance).
2. The user then converts their continuous energy model to multigroup via the:


```
model.convert_to_multigroup()
```

Python method. As part of this method, OpenMC will internally generate multigroup cross section data for each material in the problem, using one of several methods (all of which involve a short continuous energy MC calculation). A `mgxs.h5` file containing the multigroup cross section library is output for later re-use.

3. The user then converts their multigroup Monte Carlo model to a random ray model, by calling the:

```
model.convert_to_random_ray()
```

Python method. This method analyses their model and determines good default parameters for the random ray solver.

4. The user may optionally apply one or more “subdivision” meshes to their problem, so as to subdivide the geometric cells of the original model into smaller regions to improve the accuracy of the random ray solver. OpenMC uses a “cell-under-voxel” treatment, such that the original material boundaries in the problem are still fully respected. The applied mesh only subdivides existing cells — it does not remesh or homogenize anything. Any type of OpenMC mesh can be used for subdivision (regular, rectilinear, cylindrical, spherical, or unstructured).
5. The user then adds an OpenMC `WeightWindowGenerator` to their model, specifying that they want to compute global or local FW-CADIS weight windows on a given mesh.
6. The user then runs their random ray model. As a result, a `weight_windows.h5` file is generated, which can be loaded and used by subsequent continuous energy MC solves without knowledge of how the weight windows were generated.

The above workflow only involves the addition of 10–20 lines of Python code to a regular continuous energy Monte Carlo OpenMC model and does not introduce additional dependencies (in terms of other codes or cross section libraries) making it relatively easy to try out. Behind the scenes, when the random ray solver is run in weight window generation mode, it will perform two solves automatically — one in forward mode, and one in adjoint mode. While external sources (or eigenvalue fission sources) are used as normal in the forward solve, the adjoint solve will always be run in fixed source mode using a source term defined as $1/\phi_f$, where ϕ_f is the forward flux in that cell and energy group that was computed in the previous solve. This “inverse forward flux” source is used verbatim when making weight windows with the goal of global variance reduction with FW-CADIS. The user is alternatively able to indicate they want “local” FW-CADIS weight windows, in which case the adjoint source is set to zero in all source regions except for those that the user has specified. By default, cells are considered as being a “target” for local variance reduction if there exists a non-mesh tally for that region, though in the future the API may be enhanced to allow the user to manually specify material, cell, or universe IDs that they wish to use as targets.

We note that the FW-CADIS methodology (detailed in [2]) outlines consistent techniques for defining weight windows and source biasing parameters, though source biasing is not used in this analysis. As discussed by Greisheimer in [10], inconsistency between the sampled particle weight (1.0 without source biasing) and the values for the weight window that the particle is born in can cause extreme splitting immediately after sampling, resulting in low numerical efficiency. However, OpenMC does achieve consistency without source biasing by simply recording the weight window midpoint value each particle is born in (W_p). When weight window operations are performed, weight window bounds are scaled based on the particle’s starting value W_p . In practice, this scheme eliminates at-birth splitting events without altering the numerical weight of the particle, achieving consistency and numerical efficiency.

To date, the random ray FW-CADIS workflow in OpenMC has not been tested rigorously on eigenvalue problems or fission reactor geometries. While fission simulations are often focused on estimating the k-eigenvalue and the power distribution within the reactor itself, many analyses require a global flux distribution outside of the core and in the surrounding shielding material, for instance to compute dose

rates to personnel and materials, or to compute detector responses. To this end, we will examine the performance of the OpenMC FW-CADIS random ray workflow in simulating a full core reactor problem with significant shielding surrounding it.

3. TEST CASE

In previous work with OpenMC by Zammataro et al., a lead-cooled fast reactor (LFR) model resembling the *newcleo* LFR-AS-30 reactor was introduced [11]. This model features a MOX-fueled core and a target thermal power of 100 MW_{th}. While some details have been simplified to remove proprietary design aspects of the real LFR-AS-30 reactor, it retains its basic characteristics and presents a similar level of challenge in terms of shielding. As pictured in Figure 1, the core is surrounded by a large pool of lead, which is itself surrounded by a thick concrete containment pit and capped by several layers of thick stainless steel and borated steel. In total, the simulation domain is a cylinder 10 m in height and 9 m in diameter.

Figure 1. 3D cutaway plot showing the material definition of the LFR reactor model (units in cm).

While the original model focused on determining the global flux distribution, this study introduces an extra tally challenge: estimate the flux in a small “detector-like” region of the problem. This target region is located at the top of the problem in the middle of the stainless steel (AISI 316) cap region of the reactor. The target “detector” area (also of AISI 316 stainless steel) is a cylinder that is 5 cm in radius and 50 cm high, located directly in the middle of the cap region in the centerline of the simulation.

4. WEIGHT WINDOW GENERATION

To evaluate the effectiveness of the new random ray FW-CADIS workflow, we generated several sets of weight windows with different methods. The first set of weight windows was generated using MAGIC, with parameters similar to those presented by Zammataro et al. in [11] (i.e., 10 cm resolution mesh with a single energy group), and which performed at a similar level of numerical efficiency to those in the previous work. MAGIC weight windows are fairly expensive to generate as they require running the forward Monte Carlo solver multiple times in an iterative manner, with weight windows being updated in each iteration to improve the coverage of the subsequent iteration.

We also generated two sets of weight windows with the random ray workflow: one set with regular global FW-CADIS weight windows to facilitate global variance reduction (on a 15 cm resolution mesh,

Table I. Numerical and runtime performance of various weight window generation techniques in OpenMC.

Method	WW Generation Time [core-hour]	Final Simulation Runtime [core-hour]	Global Tally Metrics		Local Detector Tally Metrics			
			Coverage	RSD <0.5	Detector Flux [cm ⁻²]	Detector Flux Rel. Std. Dev.	FOM (Excl. WW Generation)	FOM (Incl. WW Generation)
Analog MC	0	19.16	38.10%	30.86%	0	N/A	N/A	N/A
MAGIC	26.39	19.92	99.15%	97.65%	2.17E-08	15.24%	4.60E+15	1.98E+15
FW-CADIS	2.11	19.37	99.98%	99.05%	2.48E-08	23.14%	1.57E+15	1.42E+15
Local FW-CADIS	2.11	18.28	28.17%	20.99%	2.30E-08	2.24%	2.07E+17	1.85E+17

with one energy group), and one set with localized FW-CADIS weight windows, so as to target the small “detector” location at the top of the model, as described in section 3 (on a 22.5 cm resolution mesh, also with one energy group). For both of the random ray weight window generation methods, the random ray solver was run with 4 energy groups. Notably, as shown in Table I, random ray weight window generation is about $12.5\times$ faster than generation with MAGIC.

We also note that the MAGIC weight window generation time in this study (26 core-hours) is lower than reported by Zammataro et al. in [11] (132 core-hours), due to recent enhancements in OpenMC since the time of publication of [11], different hardware, and slightly different generation parameters. Specifically, our experimental branch of OpenMC used for this work features a shared secondary particle bank, allowing threads to contribute their secondary particles (e.g., those generated from weight window splitting operations) to a common secondary bank that is shared by all threads. As some particles will split far more aggressively than others based on where they are in the simulation geometry, this causes a significant load imbalance between threads, which is remedied when secondaries are allowed to be shared between threads. To accomplish this in an efficient and fully reproducible manner (regardless of the number of threads used), OpenMC adapts the shared fission bank algorithm proposed by Brown in [12] to work in the context of secondary particles, by simply adding in a concept of “secondary generations” within each statistical batch. In this scheme, particles are still transported from birth to death, but secondaries are banked and not transported until the next secondary generation begins. This allows for consistent re-ordering of the secondaries based on their parent index and progeny index, and deterministic control over which pseudorandom number generator seed each secondary is assigned.

5. RESULTS

To evaluate the efficiency of the new random ray FW-CADIS workflow, we ran the OpenMC Monte Carlo solver with each of the three weight window files as well as without any weight windows at all. In each case, the global flux distribution was tallied on a 10 cm resolution mesh. The local “detector” cell flux was also tallied. All tests were run on a dual socket AMD EPYC 9654 node with 192 cores and 384 hardware threads. As weight windows can drastically affect the runtime of the code (due to more/less severe weight window splitting effects), the particle counts and number of batches for each case were tuned to run for approximately 19 core hours in parallel on the node. In all cases, 20 inactive batches were used to converge the fission source before beginning the active iterations. Weight windows were not applied during the inactive batches.

The results of our study were tabulated in terms of several metrics. First, the runtimes (both for original weight window generation and for the final actual Monte Carlo solve) were recorded. The quality of the global tally distribution was evaluated by computing the coverage of non-zero tally bins on the overlaid 10 cm resolution tally mesh. Additionally, the percentage of mesh bins with a relative standard deviation (RSD) below 0.5 was also reported. The quality of the local detector tally solution was evaluated by computing a Monte Carlo figure of merit (FOM) of:

$$\text{FOM} = \frac{1}{\text{runtime} \times \sigma^2}, \quad (1)$$

where σ^2 is the variance of the detector tally flux. As seen in Table I, the random ray FW-CADIS weight windows were highly successful at reducing the variance of the Monte Carlo solve. Compared to analog MC, both the global weight window methods (MAGIC and FW-CADIS) resulted in particles propagating to nearly all mesh bins, whereas only 38% of mesh bins were reached with analog MC. The random ray FW-CADIS global weight windows performed slightly better than the MAGIC weight windows, with a slightly higher coverage and slightly higher fraction of cells with a RSD less than 0.5. However, these improvements are so small compared to MAGIC that additional fine-tuning of the MAGIC parameters (or additional MAGIC generating iterations) may close this gap, such that the two methods can be considered to perform comparably well on this model. While MAGIC is not adjoint driven, it is still an effective tool at generating weight windows on models like this where there are no fine streaming channels and the main challenge is in bulk shielding.

As shown in Table I, the localized FW-CADIS weight window generation technique was incredibly powerful for reducing the variance of localized quantities. The local detector flux was not able to be tallied to in the analog MC case as no particles visited it, as can be seen visually in Figure 2. The global methods delivered standard deviations here of 15–23%, while the targeted local FW-CADIS random ray weight window set produced a standard deviation of only 2%. Overall, this resulted in a FOM speedup of $45\times$ when excluding weight window generation costs, or $93\times$ when including weight window generation time. As MAGIC cannot be used for localized variance reduction in OpenMC, the localized FW-CADIS capability is therefore proven to be extremely useful in OpenMC.

For each run, we also plotted a 2D flux slice along the y-z mid plane of the reactor, as shown in Figure 2, allowing us to visualize differences in coverage. Notably, in the analog MC method, particles only migrate a few mean free paths into the concrete shielding pool surrounding the lead coolant. The localized FW-CADIS run (targeting a detector located in the top middle of the cap), demonstrates the method's ability to funnel particles efficiently towards this location. Notably, the covered area around and below the reactor contracts a little, showing that particles traveling away from the detector are promptly killed. The two global variance reduction cases (MAGIC and FW-CADIS) show excellent coverage, with only two very minor differences: 1) the MAGIC case misses cells in the bottom corners of the pool shield, which are the locations with the lowest flux in the simulation, and 2) the FW-CADIS method has slightly higher variance in the cap region, likely due to errors in multigroup cross section data for the stainless steel materials there resulting in sub-optimal weight windows being generated.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we presented an evaluation of the numerical and runtime efficiency of the recently developed random ray FW-CADIS weight window generation workflow in OpenMC. This study is the first to examine the behavior of the new OpenMC workflow on a fission reactor simulation problem. The new variance reduction workflow allowed for easy and efficient generation of weight window files, without requiring any external solvers, spatial homogenization, or remeshing. This is possible thanks to OpenMC's native random ray solver that operates on the same geometry as OpenMC's Monte Carlo solver. A simplified LFR model was used to study the efficiency of the random ray generated weight windows in comparison to the Monte Carlo MAGIC-generated weight windows. Generation of random ray weight windows was found to be extremely fast in OpenMC ($12.5\times$ faster than generation of weight windows with MAGIC), allowing for speedier workflows and more ability for the user to experiment with fine-tuning of weight window parameters. Localized FW-CADIS weight windows generated with random ray were also found to be up to $93\times$ more efficient than those generated with MAGIC weight windows, in terms of FOM reduction improvement in a detector-like tally location. In summary, the recently developed random ray FW-CADIS workflow is proven to greatly enhance OpenMC's variance

Figure 2. Flux distribution along y - z axis center line of the LFR model using various weight window files in OpenMC. All four simulations were configured to use approximately equal runtime (excluding weight window generation costs). Bright yellow indicates no tally data was generated for that mesh bin.

reduction capabilities for fission simulation problems.

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